

Water striders are fast moving. They are not usually seen in rice fields because they sense any water disturbance and are quick to flee. Water striders require

constant water supply and are numerous in paddies irrigated from rivers or reservoirs.

Species of the genus *Limnogonus* are

most numerous on the IRRI farm, which is irrigated from reservoirs year-round. *h*

Light-trap catches of rice yellow stem borer

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Light-trap catches at RRS, V. C. Farm, Mandya, indicate that seasonal appearance and population fluctuations of some important rice pests follow an annual pattern. This information helps forecast pest occurrence and time control measures.

Light-trap data collected for rice yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* Walker from 1976 to 1979 show moth emergence is similar in all years (see figure). There are three peaks of emergence each year: a low peak in February (winter generation), a moderate peak in May (summer generation), and a high peak in November (kharif generation).

The pest is most destructive about 2 weeks after the winter generation emerges and a month before the summer and kharif generations. Control measures, if necessary, should be initiated then. May and November appearances might be termed suicidal emergence, as there is little standing rice to support progenies of large populations.

Moths trapped (no. mean of 1976 - 79)

Light-trap catches of the rice yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas* Walker, RRS, Mandya, 1976-79.

Light-trap data for other rice pests were also collected. Maximum numbers of leafhoppers, planthoppers (including brown planthopper), and gall midge were trapped in May and November.

Whorl maggot, caseworm, and leaf-folder trapping did not indicate a distinct trend. Maximum catch of most important rice pests in this area was in November. *h*

Bionomics of the rice water weevil *Lissorhoptrus brevirostris* (SFFR.) in Cuba

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The rice water weevil, first reported in 1950, is a principal insect pest of rice in Cuba. Adults also feed on 34 alternate host plants, but complete development from egg to adult occurs on graminaceous species.

The life cycle from oviposition to emergence of adult is 50 days at a mean

temperature of 26.2° C. In controlled conditions, adults live an average of 714 days.

In direct field counts adults appeared in mid-March. Highest population densities of adults, larvae, and pupae occurred between May and October, when average temperatures were 20° - 27.5° C and rainfall was higher than 100 mm. Population densities of adults, larvae, and pupae are highly correlated with mean temperature ($r = 0.93, 0.99,$ and $0.81,$ respectively). Light-trap data confirmed that adults appeared between May and October. Two peaks, in June

and September, are considered two generations. The correlation between adult populations and mean temperatures in the Sancti-Spiritus rice zone was 0.80.

Although adults feed on rice leaves, injury is not economically important because, even at the highest populations, they do not remove more than 1.4% of the foliar area. Larvae cause much greater damage, destroying up to 83% of root tissue and causing 54% yield loss.

In plots where different damage intensities of larvae were simulated (15% to 60% root tissue), yield reductions obtained were 37.3% to 61.1%.

Insecticide-treated plots yielded 8.75 t/ha, untreated check plots 3.41 t/ha. *h*

Effect of spacing on leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée infestation in rice

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We studied the effect of spacing on leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée infestation in rice during January-March 1982. Variety TNAU 17005 was field tested at Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, India.

Four spacings were evaluated in six replications. Nitrogen fertilizer was applied as urea supergranules at 75 kg N/ha, P and K each were applied at 40 kg/ha. Differential leaf folder infestation was recorded 55 days after transplanting. Total leaves and total leaves infested by larvae were counted on 10 randomly selected hills in each plot (see table).

Effect of spacing on leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée infestation in rice, Coimbatore, India.

Spacing (cm)	Infestation (%)
10 × 15	36
15 × 20	26
22.5 × 20	7
30 × 20	12

Mean infestation in the plots ranged from 7 to 36%. Plants with close spacing (10 × 15 cm) recorded significantly higher infestation than plants spaced 22.5 × 20 cm and 30 × 20 cm. *h*

Pest management and control WEEDS

Efficiency of some herbicides and hand weeding for transplanted rice weed control

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Field experiments during the 1980 wet season at Palli Siksha Sadana, Visva-Bharati University, Sriniketan, tested new herbicides and herbicide combinations for their ability to suppress weeds

in transplanted rice. *Echinochloa colonum*, *Echinochloa crus-galli* (grasses), and *Ludwigia parviflora* (broadleaf) were predominant weeds in the field.

Oxyfluorfen EC effectively controlled grasses, broadleaf weeds, and sedges when applied at 0.096, 0.120, and 0.144 kg ai/ha 4 days after transplanting (DT) (see table). However, rice plants yellowed after application, and although they recovered after 2-3 weeks, crop yields were reduced.

Fluchloralin EC (0.720 ai/ha, applied 2 days before transplanting [DBV]) followed by bentazon (0.960 kg ai/ha 25 DT) produced highest grain and straw yield. Hand weeding or rotary weeding 25 and 45 DT produced similar results.

Incorporating fluchloralin EC (0.960 kg ai/ha) at puddling, 2 DBT, produced the next best yield. When no weeding was done, 39% grain yield loss was observed, compared to the best treatment. *h*

Effect of herbicides and hand weeding on weed weight and rice yield, West Bengal, India.^a

Herbicide, weeding	Application		Weed dry wt (g/m ²) 50 DT	Grain yield (t/ha)
	kg ai/ha	Time		
Oxyfluorfen EC	0.096	4 DT	12.6	2.7
Oxyfluorfen EC	0.120	4 DT	12.5	2.6
Oxyfluorfen EC	0.144	4 DT	11.8	2.9
Fluchloralin EC	0.720	2 DBT	12.9	3.3
Fluchloralin EC	0.960	2 DBT	6.0	4.0
Bentazon AS	0.960	25 DT	23.9	3.1
Bentazon AS	1.440	25 DT	20.5	3.1
Fluchloralin G - 2,4-D IPE	0.500		12.8	3.6
Fluchloralin G - 2,4-D EE	0.500			
	0.625	2 DT	12.6	3.6
Fluchloralin EC fb bentazon AS	0.720	2 DBT		
	0.960	25 DT	5.8	4.1
Fluchloralin G fb bentazon AS	0.675	2 DBT		
	0.960	25 DT	3.0	4.1
Hand weeding		25 & 45 DT	5.1	4.1
Rotary weeding		25 & 45 DT	5.2	4.0
Unweeded control			48.6	2.5
SEm ±			2.7	0.6
C.D. at 5%			8.4	1.8
CV			6%	3%

^aDT = days after transplanting, DBT = days before transplanting, G = granular, EC = emulsifiable concentrate, AS = aqueous solution, fb = followed by.

Chemical weed control in dryland rice

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In 1976-78 three chemical herbicides were evaluated for control of common weeds in dryland rice fields of eastern Uttar Pradesh. Two concentrations of active ingredient of each herbicide were compared with hand weeding and no weeding. Test plots were 5 × 2.5 m. The experimental layout was a randomized block design with treatments replicated 4 times.

Variety Narendra (IET2232) was sown at 100 kg seed/ha in rows 20 cm apart using a wheelhoe. Nutrients were applied at 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha. Half